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A neurotransmission system in human cancer.

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The system was centered on expression of the neurotrophic factor MANF. Growth factors, in particular the nerve growth factor VGF were also central components of the tumor neurotransmission system, together with hormonal signaling from the angiotensin system, classical neurotransmission from cholinergic, serotonergic, dopaminergic, adrenergic and GABAergic systems. Neuropeptides, most specifically NPY (neuropeptides Y) were also central commodities in these transactions. A minimal neurotransmission complex likely capable of primitive long-term potentiation as the basis of a broader and more organismally concerned system that described MANF expression in conjunction with. an adrenal gland-like organ in the contact of nerve growth factor signaling that supported sustained neurotransmission: from the single cell, and neurotransmission we propose is a basic and essential component of a CNS-tropic tumor signaling system that also permits coupling of reward with selection pressure and effective cancer cell division or tumor growth.

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Results

Neurotrophic factors

MANF

NDNF

CTNF

Silencing BDNF

GMFG

Growth factors

VGF

PGF

Angiotensin signaling

Agtrap

AGT

Angiopietin System

Neurotransmitters

Htr receptors (serotonin)

Chrna receptors and acetylcholine

BCHE

ACE

Dopamine system

Histamine signaling

Glutamatergic signaling

GRIK

GRM

GRIA

GRIP

Adrenergic signaling

Adenosine signaling

ADORA receptors

Gabaergic signaling

Neuropeptides

Npy

PPY

GRP

GRPR

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Cell surface receptors whose expression in sum likely supported primitive LTP (long-term potentiation).

Pentraxin receptors
Purinergic receptors
NPY

Hormones

GH
GHRHR
PTH
CSHL1
PTTG1 (pituitary)

Adrenomedullin

Other
CORT
NMU

Evidence for ion flux at the membrane analogous to functions at the surface of neurons during conduction of neuronal signals.

K channels
HCN
N channels

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Methods

GSE45827: breast cancer
GSE191230: human CNS metastasis, brain
GSE116520: glioblastoma
GSE43458: lung